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“FORMULATION AND COMPARATIVE STANDARDIZATION OF AYURVEDIC SKIN CREAM”

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present research work was to formulate and evaluated the Ayurvedic skin cream of crude drug comprising extracts of curcuma longa (Turmeric). One marketed formulation and one In house formulation were subjected to comparative standardization. There is a growing demand for herbal cosmetics in the world market and they are invaluable gifts of nature. Therefore, we tried to make an Ayurvedic skin cream containing the extract of curcuma longa in along with sandalwood oil. The extract of curcuma longa has antiseptic activity, anti-inflammatory activity, and also increases whitening of skin. The sandalwood oil increases the glow on skin and has emollient properties. Hence all these properties are beneficial to normal human keratinocytes and it is safe and stable too. Ayurvedic creams offer several advantages over other creams because of its side effects such as allergic reaction. Ayurvedic skin creams do not have any of these side effects, without any harm or unwanted effects it gives the fairness look to skin. The prepared Ayurvedic skin cream was evaluated with different parameters like appearance, Spreadability; pH, viscosity, rheological study and stability along with irritancy test. Stability parameters of the formulations showed that there was no significant variation between marketed and in house formulation during the study period. The cream was found to be more stable during stability study; thus the present study suggested that it is possible develop Ayurvedic skin cream containing herbal extract and can be used as antiseptic and for beautifying purpose.

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INTRODUCTION

'Ayurveda' is the 'science of life'. Ayurveda - Ancient Science of Indian Health, since life is synonymous with health, Ayurveda is deemed to be the 'science of human health'. Ayurveda's approach towards healing is holistic. It doesn't deal with individual organs in isolation, but treats the body as a whole. More important, it doesn't give temporary relief, but fights the disease and help get rid from them. This Ayurvedic Cream vanishes into your skin, rejuvenates and revitalizes your skin from within, leaving it soft, supple and young looking. Being pure and natural, with all the wonderful attributes of turmeric and sandalwood oil, Vicco Turmeric Cream gives the skin a radiance that mere cosmetics can't hold a light to. It also protects the skin from ultraviolet Rays of the sun and maintains the original color of pigments of your skin ^[1].

Vicco Turmeric Skin Cream is a harmonious combination of medically invaluable Turmeric with cooling and fragrant Sandalwood oil. Turmeric is a wonderful versatile root that has been in every Indian household for centuries. Its amazing properties range from flavoring curries, to sterilizing wounds, to grooming women. The cream is beneficial in fighting of acne, pimples, boils, blemishes and other common disorders of skin. Due to proven medicinal properties of its active ingredients, the Government has permitted manufacturing of Vicco products under Ayurvedic Drug License. Ayurvedic medicines are taken orally, applied locally, inhaled or fermented with. This system of treatment also undertakes surgery and process of purification, called 'Panchakarma and our formulation skin cream like that's on the observation of comparative formulation and evaluation. Now a days herbal extracts are used in the cosmetic preparations for augmenting beauty and attractiveness. Herbal cosmetics are classified on the basis of dosage form like- cream, powder, soaps, solutions, etc. and according to part or organ of the body to be applied for like; cosmetics for skin, hair, nail, teeth and mouth etc. Creams are semisolid emulsions intended for application to the skin or mucous membrane ^[2].

Role of ingredients used in formulation ^[3, to 11]

The main ingredient of Ayurvedic skin cream is turmeric. Turmeric is an excellent antiseptic. It also helps to Even out skin tone and color and it makes the skin more elastic. Stearic acid governs the consistency of the cream. It is the main ingredient in the formulation of cream. Sorbitol prevents excessive drying of the cream, which makes it useful in cosmetic product. It is used as humectant. Propyl Paraben prevent deterioration caused by bacteria and fungi. It is used as preservative. Sodium hydroxide is also used as a technical ingredient, to adjust pH and to neutralize ingredients. Sandalwood essential oil is anti-inflammatory by nature. It has a soothing effect, providing relief from internal inflammation. It provide odor to the cream.

Glycerin is used as a moisturizer to treat or prevent dry, rough, scaly, itchy skin and minor skin irritations. Lanolin is used to treat or prevent dry skin, itching or other skin irritation caused by conditions such as deeper rash, radiation therapy skin burns, and others. Borax is perfect ingredient as cleansers and toners.

Objective

The objective of this research work was to formulate the cream which does not cause any side effects or adverse reactions. The cream also acts as a fairness expert in day to day life by removing aging signs. It also possesses nutritional value which provided required nutrients to the skin.

Uses of Vicco turmeric Ayurvedic skin cream

- ❖ To treat skin infections, Boils, pimples and acne
- ❖ Antiseptic

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

The marketed Vicco turmeric cream was purchased from *Vinayak medical store, Malkapur* and the turmeric powder used for formulation of in house cream was purchased from *Om grocery store, Malkapur* having pure quality. Sandalwood oil purchased from *Ayush pharmacy, an Ayurvedic medical store, Malkapur*.

Composition of Cream

Table No.1 Composition of Vicco turmeric Ayurvedic skin cream.

Sr.no	Ingredients	Concentration
1	Turmeric	16%
2	Steric acid	15%
3	Sorbitol	3%
4	Sodium hydroxide	0.07%
5	Propyl Paraben	0.05%
6	Sandalwood oil	1.2%
7	Water	q.s

Table No.2 In house Vicco Turmeric Ayurvedic Skin Cream^[11]

Sr.no	Ingredients	concentration
1	Turmeric	16%
2	Stearic acid	18.og
3	Glycerin	3.0g
4	Lanolin	2.0g
5	Borax	1.0g
6	Water	Up to80.ml
7	Preservative	1.0g
8	Perfume	q.s

Method of Preparation^[11]**Preparation of Alcoholic Extract of Crude Drug**

Take 5 grams crude drug i.e. Turmeric in conical flask and then 100 ml of ethanol was added to it, then the conical flask was capped with aluminum foil. Then this mixture was placed for maceration for 5 days.

Preparation of Oil Phase

Steric acid (18%) and lanoline was taken into china dish and this mixture was melt at 70⁰c.

Preparation of Aqueous Phase

Water, glycerin and borax and warm to same temp.as that of melted stearic acid and lanolin. Mix the oil phases in aqueous phase with continuous stirring .Add preservative and perfume .Mix them thoroughly in order to obtain a uniform product.

Evaluation Parameters

The following parameters were checked to evaluate the Vicco turmeric cream marketed formulation and in house formulation.

Appearance^[12]

When formulations were kept for long time, it found that no change in Color of cream.

Determination of Type of Emulsion^[13]**Dilution Test**

In this test the emulsion is diluted either with oil or water. If the emulsion is o/w type and it is diluted with water, it will remain stable as water is the dispersion medium" but if it is diluted with oil, the emulsion will break as oil and water are not miscible with each other. Oil in water emulsion can easily be diluted with an aqueous solvent, whereas water in oil emulsion can be diluted with an oily liquid.

Dye Solubility Test

In this test an emulsion is mixed with a water soluble dye (amaranth) and observed under the microscope. If the continuous phase appears red, it means that the emulsion is o/w type as the water is in the external phase and the dye will dissolve in it to give colour. If the scattered globules appear red and continuous phase colourless.

PH of the Cream^[14, 12]

The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution. About 0.5 g of the cream was weighed and dissolved in 50 ml of distilled water and its pH was measured.

Homogeneity^[15, 16]

The formulation was tested for homogeneity by visual appearance and touch. The appearance of the cream was judged by its color, pearlscence and roughness and graded.

Type of Smear^[15, 16]

It was determined by applying the cream on the skin surface of human volunteer. After application of cream, the type of film or smear formed on the skin were checked.

Removal^[15, 16]

The ease of removal of the cream applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap water.

Determination of Emolliency^[15, 16]

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amounts of cream was checked.

Determination of Viscosity

The viscosity determinations were carried out using a Brookfield Viscometer using spindle number 4 at a 50 rpm at a temperature of 25°C. The determinations were carried out in triplicate and the average of three readings was recorded.

Determination of Spreadability^[16, 17]

Take about 3gm of sample applied in between two glass slides and they were pressed together to obtain a film of uniform thickness by placing 1000 gm. weight for 5 minutes. Thereafter a weight (10gm) was added to the pan and the top plate was subjected to pull with the help of string attached to the hook. The time in which the upper glass slide moves over the lower plate to cover a distance of 10 cm is noted. The spread ability (S) can be calculated using the formula.

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where,

S – Spreadability,

M- Weight tied to upper glass slide- Length moved on a glass slide

T- Time taken.

The determinations were carried out in triplicate and the average of three readings was recorded.

Acid Value^[17]

Taken 10gm. of substance dissolved in accurately weighed, in 50 ml mixture of equal volume of alcohol and solvent ether, the flask was connected to reflux condenser and slowly heated, until sample was dissolved completely, to this 1 ml of phenolphthalein. Added and titrated with 0.1N NaOH [1], until faintly pink color appears after shaking for 30Seconds.

$$\text{Acid value} = n * 5.61 / w$$

Where,

n = the number of ml of NaOH required.

w = the weight of substance.

Saponification Value^[17]

Introduce about 2gm of substance refluxed with 25 ml of 0.5N alcoholic KOH for 30 minutes ,to this 1ml of phenolphthalein added and titrated immediately ,with 0.5 N HCl

$$\text{Saponification value} = (b-a) * 28.05 / w$$

Where,

a= the volume of titrant in ml

b= the volume of titrant in ml

w=the weight of substance in gm

Preparation of Phenolphthalein Indicator (Acid/Base Indicator)^[17, 18]

Weigh about 0.5g of phenolphthalein Prepare 50% ethyl alcohol solution contained of 50mL ethanol and 50mL water. Now, dissolve the phenolphthalein in the 50% ethyl alcohol solution, Store in dropper mechanism for used.

Rheological Studies^[16, 19]

The formulated cream was found to be Pseudoplastic flow. Take affixed quantity 10gms of cream in a 10 ml beaker. Keep it impact for 1 hr. The beaker was inclined to one side see whether the cream is liquefied or not. Beaker is shaken to and for continuous 5 min and checked whether consistency has changed or not. The beaker was again tilted and checked for pour ability of the cream.

Determination of Microbial Content^[16]

1gm of cream was dissolved in nutrient agar culture and volume adjusted to 100ml with the same medium. About 10ml of sample was transferred into 100ml of nutrient agar culture broth and incubated for 18-24 hours at 43-45°C. A subculture was prepared on a plate with nutrient agar culture and incubated at 43-45°C for 18-24 hours. The growth of red, generally non-mucoid colonies of gram negative rods appearing as reddish zones indicates the presence of E.coli if not then it indicates the absence of E.coli.

Irritancy Test^[16]

Mark an area (1sq.cm) on the left hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema, was checked if any for regular intervals up to 24 hrs. and reported.

Accelerated Stability Testing^[16, 19]

Accelerated stability testing of prepared formulations was conducted for 2 most stable formulations at room temperature, studied for 7 days, at 40°C for 20 days. The formulations were kept both at room and elevated temperature and observed on 0th, 5th, 10th, 15th, and 20th day to determined various parameter (By using Remi Environmental Test Chamber ,India).

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Appearance

When formulations were kept for long time, it found that no change in color of cream (Table No.3).

Type of emulsion

This dye confirms that all formulations were o/w type emulsion cream.

PH of the Cream

The pH of the cream was found to be in range of 6-7 which is good for skin pH. All the formulations were shown pH nearer to skin required (Table No.3)

Homogeneity

Both formulations produce uniform distribution of extracts in cream. This was confirmed by visual appearance and by touch (Table No.3)

Type of smear

After application of cream, the type of smear formed on the skin were non greasy (Table No.3).

Removal

The cream applied on skin was easily removed by washing with tap water.

After feel

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amount of cream was found (Table No.3).

Viscosity

The viscosity of was cream was in the range of 27025-26012 cps which indicates that the cream is easily spreadable by small amounts of shear.

Acid value and Saponification value

The results of acid value and saponification value of all formulation were presented in Table No.5 and Table No.6 and showed satisfactorily values.

Irritancy Test

The both formulation shows no redness, edema, Inflammation and irritation during irritancy studies. These formulations are safe to use for skin (Table No.4).

Rheological studies

Rheological behavior of the cream was studied and confirmed that the cream had pseudo plastic flow behavior. All the formulations showed no thixotropic (shear thinning) characteristics.

Table No.3 Physicochemical parameters.

Sr.no	Parameters	Marketed cream	In house cream
1	Appearance	Yellowish color	Yellowish color
2	Dilution test	o/w emulsion	o/w emulsion
3	Dye test	o/w type of emulsion	o/w emulsion
4	p ^H	6.7	6.8
5	Homogeneity		
	A.By visual	Homogeneous	Homogeneous
	B.By touch	Smooth and consistent	Smooth and consistent
6	Smear	Non greasy	Non greasy
7	Emolliency	No residue left	No residue left
8	Viscosity	27025cp	26012cp
9	Spreadability	0.57gm/sec	0.66gm/sec
10	Rheological study	Pseudo plastic flow	Pseudo plastic flow
11	Microbial content	No growth of microbes	No growth of microbes

Table No.4 Irritant test.

Sr.no	Formulation	Irritant	Erythema	Edema
1	Marketed	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	In lab preparation	Nil	Nil	Nil

Table No.5 Acid value.

Sr.no	Formulation	Acid value
1	Marketed	20.25
2	In lab	38.98

Table No.6 Saponification Value.

Sr.no	Formulation	Saponification Value
1	Marketed	28
2	In Lab	27.5

Table No.7 Accelerated Stability Testing.

Days	Temperature	Formulation	Parameter						
			pH	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6
0	RT	M	6.6	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.6	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
	40 ⁰ C	M	6.7	**	NCC	*	E	NG	ES
		I	6.6	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
5	RT	M	6.5	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.5	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
	40 ⁰ C	M	6.6	**	NCC	*	E	NG	ES
		I	6.6	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
10	RT	M	6.3	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.4	**	NCC	*	E	NG	ES
	40 ⁰ C	M	6.6	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.5	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
15	RT	M	6.5	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.5	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
	40 ⁰ C	M	6.3	*	NCC	*	E	NG	ES
		I	6.3	**	NCC	*	V	NG	ES
20	RT	M	6.3	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
		I	6.4	**	NCC	**	E	NG	ES
	40 ⁰ C	M	6.4	**	NCC	*	E	NG	ES
		I	6.4	*	NCC	**	E	NG	ES

X1-Homogeneity, X2-Appearance, X3-Spreadibility, X4-After feel, X5-Type of smear, X6-Removal, **: Good, *: Satisfactory, E: Emollient, NG: Non greasy, ES: Easy, NCC: Not change in color.

DISCUSSION

In the present work, it was decided to extract and formulate Ayurvedic skin cream. The Ayurvedic skin cream was O/W type emulsion, hence can be easily washed with plane water that gives better customer compliance. Our study indicated that the marketed as well as In house formulations found to be more stable. Both formulations marketed and In house had almost constant pH, homogeneous, emollient, non-greasy and easily removed after the application. The stable formulations were safe in respect to skin irritation and allergic sensitization. The extract of curcuma longa has antiseptic activity, anti-inflammatory activity, and also increases whitening of skin. The sandalwood oil increases the glow on skin and has emollient properties. Hence all these properties are beneficial to normal human keratinocytes and it is safe and stable too.

CONCLUSION

The extract of curcuma longa, sandalwood oil was used for the preparation of cream formulation. Turmeric has great medicinal value in Indian traditional system of medicine and in Ayurvedic preparation. Stability parameters of the formulations showed that there was no significant variation during the study period. The cream was found to be more stable during stability study; thus the present study concluded that it is possible develop Ayurvedic skin cream containing herbal extract and can be used as antiseptic and for beautifying purpose.

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